

Historical Origin, Beliefs and Practices of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) Religious Movement in Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract

It is worthy of note to state that there are two Chrislam movements in Lagos namely, the *Oke Tude*: Mountain of Loosing Bondage and *Ifeoluwa*: The will of God mission. However, the most popular Chrislam movement in Lagos is the: Mounting of Loosing Bondage, founded by Samsudeen Saka. While the smaller but older Chrislam movement is *Ifeoluwa*: The will of God mission, founded by Tela Tella. Very few Christians have heard of Chrislam and don't know what it means. Chrislam began in the city of Lagos, the biggest city and sea port in Nigeria, with an estimated population of about more than seven million. For the purposes of clarification, this study discusses and focuses on the historical origin, beliefs and practices of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement founded by Samsudeen Saka for the purposes of bringing peace to the world.

Keywords: Historical, Chrislamherb, Religious Movement

History of Christianity in Lagos

The Island of Lagos was in the sixteenth century, a fishing village under the jurisdiction of the kingdom of Benin. Thus its proximity to the Yoruba country made the population by the eighteenth century predominantly Yoruba. During the time Christianity came to Yorubaland and Lagos in particular; there was no country like Nigeria. Thus Odudoye (1978) stated that “there was no political unit known as Nigeria at the time when Christianity came to Yorubaland in the middle of the nineteenth century” (p. 243).

He went further to state that it was the C.M.S which from want of a more specific name and from the whole of tribes being once subjects to the king of Yoruba was designated “Yoruba country”. Christianity came to Lagos through the Europeans, whose original mission was commerce. According to Ifemesia (1962), the missionary attempt in Yoruba land came after the signal failure of the Niger expedition in 1841. In that year the first attempt had been made to penetrate the interior of West Africa with the civilizing influences of the “Bible and the plough” a motto for which the expedition had Thomas Fowell Buxton to thank. With the failure of the

expedition which included traders, settlers, missionaries that brought upon the organizers both ridicule and discouragement, it took a lot of fervent “come over unto Macedonia and help us” by the receptive converts who had returned to Yoruba land from Sierra Leone before the C.M.S was moved again to make any attempts beyond the coastline of Africa. Before the first Christian Missionary party arrived in Yoruba land, the translation of the Bible into Yoruba had already begun. Thus Hargreaves (1965) wrote that almost all the translation and some of the editing and revision was done by Africans and not by expatriate missionaries. Some scholars are of the opinion that Lagos came in contact with Christian Europe, specifically the Portuguese, as early as the fifteenth century, even though there was no evidence of any effort made to Christianize the area until the nineteenth century.

Thus, the impact of Christianity in Lagos and Yoruba land was not felt until fourth decade of 19th century when a Yoruba slave boy, Samuel Ajayi Crowther had become a Christian convert, linguist, whose knowledge in languages became a major tool and instrument to propagate Christianity in Lagos, Yoruba land and beyond. Ajayi Crowther had knowledge of Greek, Latin, wrote books on Yoruba grammar and importantly translated part of the Bible into Yoruba. As a result of this, the local people were enthusiastic about Christianity. Thus, when Henry Townsend, a C.M.S. Clergyman with C.A. Gollmer (a German) and Bishop Crowther led a mission party of Yoruba extraction from free town to Abeokuta, religions dynamics in Yoruba land had changed significantly.

Badagry which was one of the best-known port of entry into Yoruba land, a geographical fact which had contributed to its becoming a great port from which slaves from the interior were shipped overseas was actually overtaken by Lagos in 1892 when the Portuguese captives from Portugal and Brazil began to find their way back. Slave trading was continued in Lagos even after its dissolution by the British in 1802. This was masterminded by Kosoko the slave trading king in Lagos. According to Hodder (1962), the returning slaves were badly treated at Lagos which was still greatly involved in slave trading, whereas at Badagry they were welcomed by the Chief (*Wawu*) of the Yoruba quarter. As a result of this, both the returning captives from Sierra Leone and the missionaries avoided Lagos in their Journeys to Abeokuta. The British decided to take action against king Kosoko in Lagos, and in 1851 a British naval force bombarded Lagos, expelled the slave- trading king Kosoko and installed in his place Akintoye who signed a treaty to stop the

slave trade. With the bombardment of Lagos and expulsion of the slave-trading king Kosoko, Odudoye (1978) wrote that Lagos became a free port with friendly relations to Britain, thus making Badagry to lose much of its importance to Lagos which was a better port of entry to Abeokuta. It was in that year that missionaries, following in the wake of the British gun boats, began to move into Lagos.

Though the Island of Lagos was in the sixteenth century, a fishing village under the jurisdiction of the kingdom of Benin. Its proximity to the Yoruba country made the population by the eighteenth century predominantly Yoruba. The missionaries could not even begin their work in Lagos until the British flag made the place safe for them. Rev. Gollmer, a missionary member of the C.M.S party in 1843, moved to Lagos from Badagry. Birtwhistle (1950) states that;

Freeman did not wait for instructions or permission from home; he sent an African assistant missionary to begin work there, and afterwards told the committee in London what he had done. This man was John Martin, a fanti who had been trained at Lagos for three years, and when he died suddenly he was followed by a European called Gardiner. (p. 88).

After the Methodist, Mr. Harden an American Negro came from Liberia to begin the work of the Baptist Mission in Lagos. With the ceding of Lagos to the British by Dosunmu who succeeded Akintoye, Lagos became a British colony and which made them thought of Lagos differently from the rest of the country. The missionaries that were in Lagos, operated with the consciousness that they owed no obligation to any local chief. The C.M.S for instance, according to Ayandele (1963), for all their interest in evangelizing the people with the agency of the educated recaptives, reserved all the five Anglican churches in Lagos for direct pastoral care by white missionaries until 1874.

Roman Catholic Church in Lagos owes its existence to an Italian father, Francisca Borghero. He was the leader of the Dahomey mission of the society of African missions, founded in 1856. He succeeded Mgr. Marion de Bresillac as the leader and landed in Lagos for the first time from Ouidah in Dahomey on the 17th February, 1862. According to Bane (1956), before Borghero's time, Lagos and all other Catholic communities along the coasts were visited periodically by priests from Sao Tome Island. Fr. Borghero in 1862 when he came to Lagos, organized the place as an outstation of the Dahomey Mission with its headquarters at Ouidah. In

1864 a new mission was founded in Porto Novo, and from there on, Fathers from both Ouidah and Porto Novo visited Lagos.

It was, however, in 1868 that a separate mission was opened in Lagos with father Pierre Bouch as the first parish priest. Todd (1961) recorded that the opening of a separate mission in Lagos gave the society its first really firm footing in West Africa. By 1891 Mgr. Chasse was consecrated Bishop of Lagos in Lyons, the first bishop in West Africa since the death of the society's founder in Sierra Leone. The schools built by the missionaries include;

- i. Church missionary society school, Bariga, Lagos in 1859 (the first High school in Yoruba land, and in Nigeria after amalgamation of North and Southern protectorates in 1914).
- ii. St. Gregory College, Obalende Lagos, 1876 (By R.C.M)
- iii. Methodist Boys High School, Itafaji, Lagos, 1878
- iv. Methodist Girls High School, Lagos, 1879 (By Methodist)
- v. Baptist Boys High School, Lagos, 1885.

These schools no doubt, blazed education trail with Christianity as the ultimate aim. Children enrolled in these schools were converted to Christianity, as time progressed; these converts in turn became advocates of the new religion in Yoruba land. The religion spread like wild fire that by the end of 19th century there were many Christian schools established in Lagos. The products of these schools became lightning rod that transformed and changed the society in decades that followed.

History of Islam in Lagos State

According to Shorter Encyclopaedia of Islam cited in Oraegbunam, (2006), Islam is a technical term used to denote the system of beliefs and rituals based on the Koran. It is derived from the recurrent use of the verb "*aslama*" (meaning to submit oneself) in the Koran to denote the characteristics attitude of the true believer in relation to God. Catoir (1992) states that Islam, is the religion of Mohammed, the prophet of Allah. According to Herod (1976), Islam was founded in the year 622AD and its cardinal pillars include '*al shahada*' (the creed), '*al salat*' (worship/prayer), '*al saoum*' (fasting), '*al zakat*' (almsgiving) and '*al haj*' (pilgrimage). Islam

existed many years in Nigeria before the introduction of Christianity. Nzomiwu (1989) noted that Islam penetrated into Nigeria by 11th Century AD through Kanem-Bornu Empire. The first significant contact of Islamic culture with Nigerian society dates as far back as the eleventh century AD when Mai Umme Jilmi, ruled Kanem-Bornu Empire between 1085-1097. It came to Yoruba land century before Christianity and churches were built. Yoruba came in contact with Islam around 14th and 15th century during the reign of Mansa Kankan Musa of Mali Empire. According to Fafunwa (1977), Islam predated Christianity in Nigeria by three hundred years. At the initial stage of contact between Islam and Yorubaland there was a lot of friction and acrimony, but gradually Islamic religion became well accepted by the Yoruba people. The spread was very rapid among them not merely in the major cities but even in the rural areas. Supporting Fafunwa, Awolalu (1979) wrote that Muslim communities had been established in Yoruba land before the year 1840. Islam is said to have entered Lagos from badagry. Thus Akintola (1997) states that;

When Islam received a boost in badagry in 1844 when the famous Shitta Bay arrived from Sierra Leone with about Fifty Muslim followers, they stayed in Badagry for eight years before they finally moved to Lagos in 1852 and settled permanently at Main street. (p. 220).

Islam which came to Lagos at about the same time like other Yoruba towns and received royal support from Oba Kosoko after he came back from exile in Epe, was however allowed to practice their faith openly after six years of oppression and injustice from the hands of authorities. Babalola (1978) enumerated four factors which were responsible for easy and early acceptance and spread of Islamic religion among the Yorubas. These factors include geographical, commercial, political and social factors. According to him;

Geographically, Yorubaland is located close to Niger highway and this facilitated movement of people and goods as well as exchange of ideas. Trade with North Africa was easy and these traders had to accept Islam in order to avoid harassment; Oyo, which was the heart of Yorubaland, was known for her rich agricultural products, and there was need to find markets for these products. (pp. 78-79).

Traders transported these products northwards where they came in contact with Islamic religion. Furthermore, an important trade route linked Hausaland with Badagry. Here such things as clothes, kolanuts and horses were sold. Muslim traders easily found their way to Yorubaland where they sold their wares and also spread their religion. These Muslim traders, apart from selling

their wares, also settled in such cities as Ibadan, Abeokuta, Badagry and Ijebu-Ode and because they were also missionaries, they were interested in spreading their religion. Many of the Yorubas were converted to Islam and in turn became agents of Islamization, spreading Islamic religion and influence in Yorubaland.

Political disunity and civil wars among the Yoruba states encouraged the spread of Islam among the Yorubas. Those who resisted islamization were then subjected to all forms of deprivation and subhuman treatment. They were according to Ejizu cited in Nzomiwu (1990), referred to as *ARNAA* (uncultured people) and *Maguzawa* (idolater) and were chased away to remote hinterland.

Gbadamosi (1978) wrote that “the first Friday congregational prayer *Jumat* prayer was publicly observed on a spot popularly known as Animasaun Lane” (p. 14). He went further to state that Islam soon spread to other Yoruba towns, especially, during the intra-tribal wars when there was a high demand for Islamic teachers who dubbed as both Koranic teachers and amulet makers for Yoruba soldiers during the intra-tribal wars in Yoruba land. There was a change in the life of Muslims in Lagos with arrival of two groups of repatriates namely; the *Saros* and *Agudas*. While the *Saros* were repatriates from Sierra Leone, who settled at Olowogbowo and Isale-Eko areas of Lagos and built their mosque popularly known as *Masjid Mubaraka* “the blessed Mosque” at Olowogbowo in 1861; the *Agudas* were repatriates from Brazil who settled at Bamgbose Street in Lagos Island in 1840 and built few mosques at Olosun, Alagbayun and Tairu. Islam, like Christianity also found a common ground with the natives that believed in Supreme Being; while there were some areas of agreements, Islamic teachers impressed upon their audience the need to change from worshipping idols, and to embrace Allah. Without delay, Islamic scholars started establishing koranic centers to teach Arabic and Islamic studies, and much later, conventional schools were established to educate new converts and propagate Islam.

Emphasis on the importance of education was laid by Islam. Though the colonial masters were obstacle to Islam, the idols, the Islamic education was the first form of education known in Lagos. Akintola (1997) gave a reason for the suppression of Islam when he states that Henry Carr referred to Muslims and traditionalist as “heathens and enemies to our progress” (p. 220). Thus Fafunwa (1997) asserts that “Muslim education in Nigeria was retarded not because the Muslims were unprogressive but because the colonial administration...had a phobia for Islam” (p.72). The search and acquisition of knowledge in Islam is very important. Prophet Muhammad is said to

have asked his followers to search for knowledge even if it means going to China. China here indicates long distance place to mean that knowledge could be sought for anywhere, that distance should not be taken as barrier for the acquisition of knowledge. Developments were made in education by Muslims. Thani (1997) gave examples of such developments as, surgery and pharmacology was introduced by Ibn Nusa Zuhr, Al-Achem introduced chemistry from whom the name chemistry comes, Muhammad Ibn Nusa as the first person to use decimal notation and that the numerical systems now used all over the world were introduced by Muslims.

Today in Lagos, however, Islamic way of life have affected virtually all the Muslims as some of the males prefer to dress like the Arabs wearing long gowns '*jalabiyah*' with caps, and the female wearing long head-ties Hijab while the girls uses veils and stockings together and long gowns. Among the Lagosians in recent times such Islamic names like Razaq, taofiqah are answered, while some Arabic words are used daily by Muslims in Lagos. The number of Muslims in Lagos state increase everyday while Islamic education is been taught and studied through Quranic schools in mosques and houses, and or under the shade of tree. This study is also undertaken through special organized schools like Centre for Islamic and Arabic Studies in Government owned secondary schools where Islamic studies are taught and in higher institutions, with improved methods of teaching. Islamic religion no doubt, impacted Yoruba culture in Lagos and other Yoruba states significantly. For instance, the *Ifa* (oracle) consultation is Islamized to *Istikhara* (inquires prayer), celebration of *Orisa* festival was transformed or replaced with celebrating *eid-el-fitri* and *eid-el-kabir*, women and men outlook were modified as polygamy was curtailed or modified into "four at a time" while prefixed *Orisa* names were changed to "*Olu*" (*Olorun*) plus *Bunmi* becoming *Olorunbunmi*. Traditional shrines and ritual sites were replaced with central mosques in certain areas in Lagos and major Yoruba town and cities.

History of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) Religious Movement

The founder of chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement was born into Muslim family of Alhaji Zakariyah in Ijebu-ode area of Ogun state. His educational background was not known, except the general opinion that he finished primary school and the uncertainty of whether he attended secondary school. According to Bello and Janson cited in Mgbemena (2016), Samsudeen's father is a Muslim, but was a renowned herbalist who practiced traditional medicine and was well known among the people of the same cult. They went further to state that since Saka

did not perform well at school; he decided to join his father. Samsudeen Saka who is the founder of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) was very popular too like his father in the practice of traditional medicine which he started at an early age and which he practiced for complete fifteen years, and gained the name “young wizard”. This name “young wizard” as funny it was, made Samusudeen Saka very popular and widely known. Bello and Janson cited in Mgbemena (2016) wrote that;

One of the wives of his father was a witch. The fact that her witchcraft did not affect him proves, according to Saka, his supernatural powers. A friend of his father then started calling him Samsudeen Saka young wizard. This name turned out to be a good name for publicity and soon Saka gained a name for himself as an herbalist. (p. 3).

Another means through which Samsudeen acquired fame was through a television programme called *Eweje*, which he featured in the mid-1980s. He based his healing method on traditional medicine, which was different from what is common among his fellow herbalist and practice what could be termed as a modernized way of applying traditional medicine in which the use of herbs is a central feature. Even though he made use of herbs, he claimed that he and his family were never involved in the worship of idol.

In an interview with Saka, Janson (2011) wrote that;

The vision to bring mutual understanding between Muslims and Christians was revealed to me by the Almighty God, when I rested near the Ka'aba. In a dream, God showed me photographs of religious intolerance in Nigeria, and he assigned me to bridge the misunderstanding between the two religions. (p. 7).

The establishment and emergence of this new religious movement was by Bola in Mgbemena (2016) characterized by three different divine calls at different intervals. The first divine call received by Samsudeen was when he went for pilgrimage at Mecca in 1979 when he was performing *Tawaf* circumbulation round *ka'bah*, the house of God. It was as a result of his background as a Muslim and his belief in Allah that made him embark on several pilgrimages to Mecca to perform *Hajj*. It was during his performance of *Hajj* that he heard a voice call his name three times, but did not answer. However, it was on the third time that the voice asked him to go and unite both Christians and Muslims in Nigeria together. Bello and Janson (2013) wrote that he received a divine call by *Allah*, telling him that he had to unite Christians and Muslims by

enlightening them that they are serving the same God, but in different ways. He was asked to remind both Christians and Muslims that the essential pillar of any religion is love.

Prior to the revelation, the founder of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) before going to Mecca was not at peace and happy about the inter-religious crises between Christianity and Islam, the unhealthy competition that existed amongst them, the supremacy struggle amongst them. Even though he got the revelation in Mecca, the name Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) was revealed to him when he came back from Mecca. Samsudeen Saka initially did not know how to deliver the message he received from God after his divine call. The first obstacle he encountered was that although he was a Muslim by birth, he did not have any formal education in Islam. He is also limited in the knowledge of the Bible. What made his task easier was that as an herbalist many Christians, and even none Muslims used to consult him. It was from there, that he then coined the name Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*), referring to the Christians and Muslims consulting him for herbs to cure their ailments which include physical, spiritual, social and financial ailments. At the initial time, this name was somewhat confusing and was seeing by some people as the founder mixing Christianity, Islam and traditional Yoruba religion in a heretic trinity.

The second divine call received by Samsudeen Saka, was in March, 1995. This time around and in this revelation he was asked to change his herbal method of healing to the spiritual method by means of prayer. According to Idowu in Mgbemena (2016), Saka was said to have gotten the revelation for the new way on a night vigil, the starting date of his seven days trance. This revelation is said to be the true message of God. However, this did not go down well with some of his supporters and followers who could not support the new idea and thus left the movement. Adesina (2004) wrote that “at this stage, the founder and his followers began to adjust, though they were still practicing traditional medicine, but engaging more and more in spiritual exercise than before”(p. 85).

The third call which was, however, a clearer message to the second call was received on February, 1997. Idowu in Mgbemena (2016) states that the founder was asked this time to do away with traditional medicine so that he would submit to the will of God. This was a major decision he was to take because it involves him abandoning his healing home which was his only means of livelihood. In as much as he does not want to abandon his healing means of living, he also did not want to go contrary to God’s directive in the form of disobedience. Based on this, he had to meet severally with his father and his fellow trained traditional doctors to discuss on what decision to

take and how to go on with the decision. After several meeting with his father and his fellow trained traditional doctors who never supported the idea, he countered them by saying that if they could submit to the will of God, He is ready to take control of their problems and concluded that the will of God should be done. This decision was followed by an official announcement which he made on the preceding Sunday to his congregation, that God commanded him to make do with traditional medicine. Not necessarily that traditional medicine is bad, but that God wants him to work in another way for him. Sandra (2015) noted that Saka was formerly a successful and respected practitioner of alternative medicine. That it was while in Mecca in 1989 for his obligatory pilgrimage, he was called by the creator to initiate this mission of reconciliation.

This announcement was followed by mixed reactions from the members, as the trustees were in support of the great command while over eighty per cent of the members were against the change. This did not come as a surprise to Saka as he expected that there will be divergent view to his announcement. What actually surprised Samsudeen Saka and shocked him was the action of his eighteen coordinators and six deputy coordinators that conspired against him so that they can ruin the mission. These were people who underwent through series of management training under his leadership, but now want to ruin his mission. Adesina (2004) wrote that;

Wonders began to exhibit themselves in their clearest possible forms as their hopes were shattered. The faith of the remaining members began to move and move strong daily. That within a short time, three of the separated coordinators came to repent and, therefore joined hands with collective responsibility under the leadership of the founder. (p. 88).

Beliefs and Practices of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) Religious Movement

Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement is characterized with several belief systems and practices. Though members of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement mixed Christian and Muslim elements in their religious beliefs and practices they do not entirely drop their Christian or Muslim identity. Thus everyone according to Saka (cited by Janson, 2013), is welcomed in the mission, be they Christians or Muslims. Some people believe that Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) is a doubtful faith, because of its synthetic nature; this is because they believe and are of the view that Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) does not have special scripture to explain and defend. However, what Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) sets to achieve is unity amongst the warring religions (Christianity and Islam), and thus does not make use of a particular scripture but both scriptures

of Christians and Muslims. Therefore, the beliefs in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) are in the areas that both Christianity and Islam have in common and preach. These areas which both religions have in common and which forms the basis of belief in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) are belief in the existence of God, love, Jesus and prayer, Angels and prophets, Satan and demons, sin and forgiveness, fasting and pilgrimage, almsgiving, repentance and judgment day.

In the doctrine of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*), the Bible and the Quran are viewed as equal, and in a service reading is done from both of them. People are free to call on Allah or God when they pray. In the music worship part, Christian and Islamic hymns are sung. Holidays like Christmas, Easter, Ramadan and other Christian and Islamic holidays are equally observed. In their place of worship there is an altar built and worshippers can come before this altar and seek God in prayer. Members are trained in evangelism and are working to convert outsiders to their faith.

i. Belief in the Existence of God

The founder and members of the Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement believe in the existence of one God. Nmah (2012) states that, “God’s nature is far beyond our limited conception. If God is a being, that which nothing greater can be conceived then it follows that He must be the ULTIMATE goal of every mankind” (p. 226). Both Christianity and Islam affirm their utmost belief in existence of one Supreme Being, God the creator. The Quran teaches absolute monotheism and proclaims that God is a transcendent being, creator, sustainer of the universe. He is called the Great seer, Reckoner, Pardoner, Keeper and Guide. Thus the belief in the unity of God is called ‘*Tawhid*’.

According to Nzomiwu (1989), the oneness of the work of God means that none has the power to the works which God has done or which he may do. He is Omnipotent. He went on to state that the unity of Allah is well summarized by Surah 112 which says;

“He is God, The one and only, God the eternal,

Absolute; He begetteth not, Nor is He begotten;

And there is none like unto Him”.

The omnipotent and creative power of God is proclaimed by the Quran where it states that God gives life and death. Islam not only stresses, in the most effective manner, the unity of God;

it also enables us to have a glimpse of the splendour of divine attributes. Just like the Muslims believe in the existence of one God, Christians also do not believe in the existence of many Gods. Christians are deep-rooted in their belief of one God. This is as a result of the Jewish monotheistic background, from which Christianity emerged. Even though most Christians view the concept of God as consisting of three beings in one-God the father, God the son and God the Holy Ghost, it is still a mystery and a very difficult concept because human analogies cannot be used to express spiritual matters.

However, Christians do not believe in the existence of three Gods, but the issue of Trinity is just a concept developed from implied understanding of God. What Christians believe in, is the existence of one Almighty God. Thus Chrislamherb religious movement just like Christians and Muslims believe in the existence of one true God.

ii. Belief in Love

In Chrislamherb religious movement, love is the pivotal bedrock of the movement. The foundation of Chrislamherb religious movement is on love. In Christianity, the greatest of all the commandments of God is love. Commenting on that, Nebechukwu (1993) while making reference to the Bible states “This is my commandment: love one another as I have loved you” (John 15:12). In accordance with this, Paul stresses that without Christian love, no gift of charism, no devotion or energy is of any value at all (1 Cor.13:1-3). The highest example of love for Christians is the love exemplified and displayed by Christ death on the cross for the salvation of mankind.

According to Mgbemena (2012), the Quran teaches love which compares favourably with the Christian teaching on love of God and that of our neighbour. According to the Quran, Righteousness is he who believes in Allah and gives away wealth out of love of God to the near kin, the Orphan, the needy, the wayfarer and to those who ask. It further stresses that kindness and charity towards others should be at all times and even in adversity. Quran 4: 36 states;

And be good to the neighbour

Who are near

Neighbour who are strangers.

The companion by your side

The wayfarer (ye meet)
And what your right hand possess
For Allah loveth not
The arrogant, the vain glorious.

Mgbemena (2012) also wrote that the Quran teaches that man has a dual responsibility to discharge in moral order. These are his relation to Allah and his relation to himself and the external world. These two types of responsibilities are not to be regarded as exclusive, but are merely two sides of the same coin. A Muslim adequately fulfils his moral obligations to Allah by surrendering himself totally to Allah in faith, and fulfills the other obligation by developing social conscience and in caring for the welfare of other. The discharge of this dual responsibility is *khair* or good and failure to do this is *sharr* or evil. Chrislamherb religious movement believes that love is the most important of all the commandments, which if both Christians and Muslims have love for each other, there will be no tension and war between the two. Thus in Chrislamherb religious movement Christians are obliged to respect and care for Muslims and Muslims on the other hand have to listen to Christians for the sake of love and peaceful co-existence.

iii. Belief in Jesus and Prayers

Jesus Christ was mentioned ninety three (93) times in the Quaran. Jesus Christ is seeing as the word of God by Christians as noted in the Bible. While the Muslims also as noted in the Quaran believes that Jesus is a word from God, a spirit from God. Eventhough there is controversy over his divinity; the Quran supports his miraculous birth and both believers that Jesus Christ is a historical person recognizing him as a vehicle of god's revelation. Chrislamherb religious movement believe also in Jesus Christ with the full knowledge of the area of controversies and differences between Christianity and Islam. With the knowledge of the areas of differences Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement does not focus on those differences but remain silent over the most controversial questions.

iv. Belief in Angels and Prophets

There is a belief in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement on the existence of Angels. This belief is in line with the teaching and belief in both Christianity and Islam on the

existence of angels who are believed to be beings created by God. There is also this belief among Christians and Muslims on the existence of prophets. However, the variation lies in the number of prophets that both religions subscribe to. While the Quran according to Adesina (2004), mentions twenty five (25) prophets and no prophetess at all, the Bible mentions thirty nine (39) prophets and five (5) prophetesses.

v. Belief in Satan and Demons

Christianity and Islam believe in the existence of satan and demons. In Islam satan is called *Shaytan* and demon *Jinn*. According to Nzomiwu (1989);

Jinns are being created from fire, unlike the angels that are created from light. They are a certain class of beings that cannot be perceived with senses. Their function is described as that of exciting evil passion or low desires. (pp. 111-112).

Commenting further on demons, Nzomiwu (1989) stated the duties of the demons as:

- i. Leading people astray
- ii. Opposing the prophets, and
- iii. Teaching men sorcery.

Thus all evil thoughts and actions are attributed to them and they do not have access to God's secrets. Both religions believe in the existence of Satan and demons as not having anything good to offer to humans. Thus Chrislamherb religious movement believes in the existence of Satan and Demons, and are believed to be agents of destruction.

vi. Belief in Sin and Forgiveness

According to the Orthodox teaching in Islam as stated by Mgbemena (2012), there are two kinds of evil namely little or venial sins and great or capital sins, which are recognized by the Quran. The *Murijites*, however teach that all sins are little and do not harm man as long as he is a Muslim. The *Kharijites* on the contrary hold that all sins are great and that every sin is an act of infidelity and as such the sinner should be excluded from the Islamic Community or even killed. The Christians also believe in sin, which they see also as going or behaving in contrary to the

preaching and teachings of Christ. Christians believe that sin brings about shortfall to God's glory and thus preaches against it.

Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement believes in, and preaches forgiveness. Sin and forgiveness are one of the major basic concepts of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*). Thus it is believed in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*)religious movement that committing sin does not mean that the human heart is dead. This is because human being is imperfect and therefore commits sin always consciously or unconsciously. Also deep rooted in their belief is the act of forgiveness. It is believed in the movement that it is only with a forgiving spirit that Christians and Muslims can come together for common spiritual service under the umbrella of the new faith.

vii. Fasting and Pilgrimage

Fasting which is and involves total abstinence from food, drink or other material desires of flesh, for the purposes of punishing the flesh and spiritual growth is preached by both Muslims and Christians. In Islam it is called *saum* and consists of total abstinence from food, drink and cohabitation from sunrise to sunset. It is recommended by the Quran for all Muslims; "O believers, prescribed for you is the fast, even as it was prescribed for those that were before you so that you may guard against evil" (Surah 2:183). Nzomiwu (1989) wrote that the institution of fasting was established in the second year after *Hijrah*, and listed the various kinds of fast as;

- i. Obligatory Ramadan fast
- ii. Atoning or redeeming fast which is observed at another time in place of the one which has been omitted.
- iii. Expiatory fast by way of expiation for breaking certain circumstances.
- iv. Vowed fast, a fast vowed to be observed under certain commandments or for some sin committed.
- v. Supererogatory fast, including all kinds of voluntary fast.

This institution is circumscribed to by Christians and was said to have originated from Christ's mandate to his disciple. Also a belief in Christianity is a regular/yearly visit to Jerusalem which is believed to be their Holy land. Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement believes in fasting and performs their pilgrimages at both Jerusalem and Mecca.

viii. Almsgiving

Almsgiving for both Christianity and Islam is the act of giving away one's wealth to the poor and the needy. This act of almsgiving for both religions is intended to do away with inequalities in the society. Acting as a levelling influence but also as means of developing the higher sentiments of man, the sentiments of compassion, love, fairness, sympathy towards fellow human beings. Both Quran and Bible stress that blessing comes upon anyone who gives their wealth voluntarily. According to Nzomiwu (1989);

Voluntary almsgiving should be done in such a way that it does not convey the idea of superiority of the giver or the inferiority of the receiver. It should not be followed up with reproaches. It may be given openly or secretly but it is better done secretly. (p. 88).

Both religions believe in voluntary and obligatory kind of almsgiving. In Christian religion the obligatory almsgiving is in the form of tithe and thus called tithing. While in Islamic religion, it is called *Zakat*. This obligatory form of almsgiving, practiced by the two religions has to do with giving out a certain percentage of one's wealth. In Islam Abdul cited in Mgbemena (2016) wrote that "it is charged annually on property which has remained in the possession of a person for a whole year when its value has reached a certain limit called *Nisab*" (p. 60). The Quran states that alms are only for the poor, the needy, and the officials appointed for its collection, and those whose hearts are made to incline to truth and captives and those in debt and for the cause of God, and the way farer. This belief is also adopted by the Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement.

ix. Repentance

Both Christianity and Islam believe in repentance after sin. They believe that it is only repentance that can restore man's dignity with God. The Quran teaches that a Muslim is supposed to repent immediately after committing sin because delay constitutes in itself a sin. That repentance should also take place before the hour of death because some traditions hold that repentance at the hour of death is of no avail. According to Mgbemena (2012), true repentance comprises of;

- i. A change of heart
- ii. Being sorrowful for offending God and
- iii. Mankind amends.

Only those who show true repentance are forgiven. Based on this Adesina (2004) wrote that the only key to enter into the room of success is to repent with sincerity. Quick (1990) also stated that repentance is generated in the heart of men because the greatest triumph revealed through the crucifixion is to overrule sin itself for some good which could not otherwise have been. Forgiveness of those who show true repentance could be either that God pardons their sins and therefore does not punish them for it or he conceals them from the eyes of the angels and wipes them out from the book of account. If a Muslim eventually dies without repentance, it is up to God to decide whether to punish him or pardon him because God can forgive all sins except polytheism. Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement believes in the act of repentance.

x. Righteousness

Righteousness is a belief in both Christianity and Islam. Thus members are encouraged to live a righteous life. Righteousness in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) is based on love of God without any shade of worldly motives or preferential treatment where in faith Muslims and Christians serve God under the same canopy without any atom of discrimination. As a result of this, Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement believes in and preaches that true faith is the source of truth and good deeds. Thus true righteousness in the religious belief of Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) lies in the Christian and Muslim faith serving God under the same canopy without an iota of discrimination.

xi. Belief in Justice and Peace

Christianity and Islam believe in Justice and Peace. In Islam, the highest level of Justice is to do justice without demanding it, recognizing that our own demands may be the cause of the imbalance itself. It is a belief in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement that both Christians and Muslims are equal in the sight of God. With a little addition to the belief of peace and justice in Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement, is the principle of according to Adesina (2004), equal worth of both Christianity and Islam. Thus Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement believes because of the ones ideology of the founder that Christians and Muslims are equal before God even though with differences in doctrine which he preaches that they should rise above those doctrinal differences for the sake of peace and justice.

xii. Belief in Judgment Day

The belief of accountability is upheld by both Christianity and Islam. Both religions believe that there is always a day when one will give account of his/her life on earth. This belief on the day of accountability hitherto brings to the fore, the knowledge of the existence of heaven and hell, where everyone will go depending on the kind of account of life given by a person. Both religions believe that good deeds are rewarded with Heaven, while bad deeds or doers of evil will be sent to Hell. Thus heaven is always associated with good actions and hell with bad actions. With the knowledge of the existence of this, members of both religions are always encouraged to indulge and engage in good actions in order to merit heaven.

Mgbemena (2012) states that;

one of the fundamental assertions of the Quran which no doubt influences and colours the ethical life of every Muslim is that there is a day of judgment at the end of the world, and that on that day God will judge men and send them to either paradise or hell. (p. 2-4).

As a result of this, Muslims imbued the spirit of accountability which became the guiding principle behind their conduct. They are taught that even if they escape human punishment for their sins or crimes in this world, they are bound to face the divine punishment in the next. This is because Allah does not waste the reward of the doer of good. Good deeds are subscribed to both faiths and the adherents are expected to do good works. The dimension of good deeds in both faiths are numerous, far reaching and comprehensive. With this, the believers have to guard their external behaviour and manifest deeds. Hashim (1990) wrote that the moral codes or commandments in both religions are designed to build in the human being a sound mind, peaceful soul, a strong personality and a healthy body. Chrislamherb (*Oke Tude*) religious movement therefore believes and advocates for good conduct from its members for proper accountability on the Judgment day.

Conclusion

It is interesting to note that in Nigeria, ethnicity and religious bigotry has become a fulcrum of various forms of nationalism ranging from assertion language, cultural autonomy and religious superiority to demands for political autonomy and self-determination. All these often times lead to some forms of contextual discrimination of members of one ethnic or religious group against another on the basis of differentiated systems of socio-cultural symbols and religion. Thus in multi-

ethnic and religiously diverse society like Nigeria, with some forms of contextual discrimination, relationships between people may be characterized by lack of cordiality, mutual suspicion and fear as it is the case among the various components. It is as a result of, and on this basis that Samsudeen Saka founded the Chrislamherb - Religious movement, with the purpose of restoring the lack of cordiality, eradicating mutual suspicion and fear among people especially the various religious components. It proposes a model to escape mono-religious approaches.

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